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Corresponding Author: Dr Guillermo Zaragoza, Ph.D.

Corresponding Author's Institution: CIEMAT

First Author: Patricia Palenzuela, PhD student

Order of Authors: Patricia Palenzuela, PhD student; Diego César Alarcón, PhD; Julián Blanco, PhD; Elena Guillén, PhD student; Mercedes Ibarra, PhD student; Guillermo Zaragoza, Ph.D.

Abstract: Different alternatives for the effective combination of desalination technologies into concentrating solar power (CSP) plants in the Mediterranean area are discussed and evaluated. Two cases are considered where a low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) plant is integrated into a CSP plant replacing the condenser of the power cycle. In one case, a low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) plant is fed by steam at the outlet of the turbine expanded to 70 °C. In the other case a LT-MED is fed by the steam obtained from a thermal vapour compressor (LT-MED-TVC) which uses the exhaust steam of the CSP plant (at 37 °C, 0.063 bar) together with some extracted from the turbine at higher pressure (17 bar). The two cases are compared with that of a reverse osmosis (RO) unit powered by the electricity produced by the CSP plant. In this case, two different wet cooling technologies, once-through and evaporative water cooling, and a dry air cooling are considered for the CSP plant. Thermodynamic simulations are presented for all cases, together with an economic analysis.

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Editor
Desalination Journal

Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Desalination journal.

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“Evaluation of suitable configurations for combining solar power and desalination plants in the Mediterranean area”

Authors:

Patricia Palenzuela, Diego C. Alarcón Padilla, Julián Blanco, Elena Guillén, Mercedes Ibarra, Guillermo Zaragoza.

Affiliation:

CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería, Ctra. de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain.

Yours, sincerely

Guillermo Zaragoza

Environmental Applications of Solar Energy
Plataforma Solar de Almería
Carretera de Senés km. 4; P.O.BOX 22
04200 Tabernas (Almería), Spain
Phone: (+34) 950 387941
Fax: (+34) 950 365015
Email: guillermo.zaragoza@psa.es
URL: www.psa.es

Suggested Reviewers

- Nicolas Galanis. Email: nicolas.galanis@usherbrooke.ca
- Juan Carlos Bruno. Email: juancarlos.bruno@urv.net
- Mohamed Darwish. Email: darwish@kuc01.kuniv.edu.kw

Highlights

- Different alternatives for the combination of desalination technologies into CSP plants in the Mediterranean area are discussed and evaluated.
- The integration of a LT-MED into a CSP plant is more efficient than a LT-MED-TVC, both replacing the condenser.
- Connecting a RO unit to a CSP plant results more efficient than the most optimum CSP+MED coupling.
- The use of evaporative cooling for CSP+RO is the most efficient and economical in terms of electricity production.
- The electricity costs for once-through wet and dry cooling systems are higher than those of the CSP+MED coupling.

Abstract

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Evaluation of suitable configurations for combining Solar Power and Desalination Plants in the Mediterranean area

Patricia Palenzuela, Diego C. Alarcón Padilla, Julián Blanco, Elena Guillén, Mercedes Ibarra, Guillermo Zaragoza*

CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería, Ctra. de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain.

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 950387941; fax: +34 950365015. E-mail address: guillermo.zaragoza@psa.es

Abstract

Different alternatives for the effective combination of desalination technologies into concentrating solar power (CSP) plants in the Mediterranean area are discussed and evaluated. Two cases are considered where a low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) plant is integrated into a CSP plant replacing the condenser of the power cycle. In one case, a low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) plant is fed by steam at the outlet of the turbine expanded to 70 °C. In the other case a LT-MED is fed by the steam obtained from a thermal vapour compressor (LT-MED-TVC) which uses the exhaust steam of the CSP plant (at 37 °C, 0.063 bar) together with some extracted from the turbine at higher pressure (17 bar). The two cases are compared with that of a reverse osmosis (RO) unit powered by the electricity produced by the CSP plant. In this case, two different wet cooling technologies, once-through and evaporative water cooling, and a dry air cooling are considered for the CSP plant. Thermodynamic simulations are presented for all cases, together with an economic analysis.

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1. Introduction

Currently, 80% of Europe's primary energy supply is based on fossil fuels. This contributes to negative environmental and economic impacts and makes Europe vulnerable to energy supply disruptions from energy imports and volatile energy price developments. One energy technology that could play a major role in a fast and efficient transformation to renewable energies is concentrating solar power (CSP) [1]. In order to make the most efficient use of solar energy, regions with high solar irradiance are selected as prospective locations for CSP plants. The Mediterranean area is a good candidate with high values of DNI radiation (1300 kWh/m²·yr in the coastal areas and 3200 kWh/m²·yr in the South and deserts areas) [2]. As a matter of fact, large solar development plans and projects, such as the Desertec Initiative [3] and the Mediterranean Solar Plan [2], which consider the installation of CSP plants in the Mediterranean area, are currently under discussion and preparation.

On the other hand, typical geographical coincidence of water shortage and high solar radiation is widely recognized [4]. This is the case of the Mediterranean region, which increasingly suffers from a serious lack of fresh water supplies. Drivers for the lack of fresh water include unsustainable extraction of existing fresh water resources, climate change effects leading to increased droughts, a fast growing population and economic development which require an increased availability of potable water for drinking water, industrial processes and irrigation.

The use of solar energy to simultaneously address water and power production is one of their most sustainable solutions. Therefore, the integration of water desalination technologies in concentrating solar thermal power plants is a relevant research area, and if successful, will certainly accelerate the large-scale implementation of solar energy in the Mediterranean area. In this context, reverse osmosis (RO) and multi-effect distillation (MED) have been preselected as the most promising desalination technologies for the coupling to solar power plants ([1]).

Several studies on basic integrated power and desalination plants configurations have been published. Olwig [5] performed a techno-economic study for the combination of parabolic trough power plants for electricity and water production with MED and ultrafiltration/RO plants in two sites in Israel (Ashdod) and Jordan (Aqaba). Both integrated systems use a wet cooling system and the same fresh water and electricity production were taken into account. The results showed that the configuration with RO had economic benefits in comparison to CSP+MED configuration except for very high electricity prices. It

was concluded that the results strongly depend on the technical and economic input parameters, so in order to evaluate the costs in detail it is necessary to consider all boundary conditions. Another technical and economic study for water desalination and CSP power plants in different MENA countries considered a dry cooling system for the turbine [6]. For each location, four configurations were analyzed, combining two types of solar technologies (parabolic trough and linear Fresnel reflector) and two types of desalination processes (LT-MED and RO). The main result was that in most cases studied the solar field required for the CSP+RO was larger than for the CSP+LT-MED, due to the higher electrical consumption of the RO overcompensating the lower thermal efficiency of the turbine of the MED case. Schmitz ([7]) proposed an analysis with tailor-made simulation models for parabolic trough solar power plants in combination with multi-effect distillation and reverse osmosis, using the seawater properties of the Gulf of Almería (in the Mediterranean Sea) for the performance simulation of the desalination plants. The analysis aimed at the determination of authentic values of annual electricity and water production, auxiliary energy consumption and cost for investments, operation and maintenance of the cogeneration plants. The investigated configurations were compared in different operation modes of the solar power plant regarding levelized water costs and their composition. It was concluded that reverse osmosis was the most suitable technology for seawater desalination in combination with parabolic trough solar power plants. However, the different refrigeration modes were not evaluated.

Regarding the cooling system in the CSP plant, today's solar thermal power plants are similar in design to conventional power plants and typically use wet cooling. The condensation of the exhaust steam from the turbine can be made with dry or wet cooling. Two different cooling technologies for a power cycle of 50 MW_e solar thermal power plant were compared from an exergetic point of view ([8]). The first design configuration used a cooling tower while the second configuration used an air cooled condenser. It was concluded that from an exergetic point of view, the use of an air cooled condenser was not an efficient solution for working at low exit turbine pressures, which is the case of the Mediterranean area. However, it became more competitive at the higher pressures corresponding to much warmer regions. Wet cooling for thermoelectric power plants is accomplished using two methods: once-through cooling and evaporative water cooling. Once-through cooling uses large volumes of water (usually seawater and in quantities in the order of 90000-100000 m³/MWh). This produces an environmental impact by returning at a higher temperature and can be a limiting factor if the water source is not refreshed enough. On the other hand, evaporative water cooling requires a constant supply of freshwater, as it consumes most of the water directly through evaporation. A representative wet-cooled parabolic trough plant located in the Mojave Desert, California, consumes about 3 m³/MWh [9]. However, for sites that have a limited supply of water the use of dry air cooling to condense the exhaust steam of the turbine is more suitable, since it reduces the water consumption of the CSP plant to about 0.300-0.340 m³/MWh ([10]). The drawbacks of the dry cooling systems are: a significant reduction in power output, an increase in parasitic power requirements, and higher capital costs ([11]).

This paper addresses the techno-economic analysis of different concepts for integrating solar power plant and desalination unit in the Mediterranean region. The simultaneous production of water and electricity by a RO plant connected to a CSP plant is the most straightforward option. In this case, different wet cooling technologies have been evaluated and compared: once-through and evaporative water cooling, and a dry air cooling system. However, the integration of a low temperature MED unit into a CSP plant is an interesting alternative to be considered, since it allows to replace the conventional cooling unit of the power cycle by using the exhaust steam as the thermal source of the desalination plant. This way, the energy which would otherwise be dissipated in the cooling of the power cycle is used to produce water, which has an added value for the combined system. However, in order to satisfy the demand of the low-temperature MED for a good performance, the input steam must be at about 70°C (corresponding to 0.031 bar), which means that the steam of the turbine is not left to expand completely and therefore the efficiency of the power cycle is decreased. This is why another alternative is considered using thermo-compression. In this case, the steam is left in the turbine to expand fully but then is combined in a steam ejector with steam at higher temperature taken from an extraction of the turbine in order to reach the input conditions of the MED. The thermodynamic analysis comprises simulations of the integrated power and desalination facility and of the solar field required in each configuration. For the economic evaluation, an estimation of the Levelized Electricity Cost (LEC) and the Levelized Water Cost (LWC) has been carried out.

2. Methodology

2.1 Description of the systems

The different systems under consideration are:

- Configuration 1: RO unit connected to a parabolic trough solar power (PT-CSP) plant (see Fig. 1).
- Configuration 2: LT-MED unit integrated into a (PT-CSP) plant (see scheme in Fig.2).
- Configuration 3: LT-MED-TVC unit integrated into a PT-CSP plant (see Fig. 3).

The CSP plant consists of a large field of single-axis parabolic-trough solar collectors (LS3 type) aligned on a north-south orientation and a thermal storage tank to provide additional operation when solar radiation is not available. The collectors can track the sun from east to west during the day to ensure it is continuously focused on the linear receiver. Two cooling systems (once-through and evaporative water cooling) and a dry air cooling one are considering for condensing the exhaust steam from the turbine in the power block.

As can be observed in Figs. 1-3, steam at A is generated from the thermal energy collected by the solar field. It is subsequently sent to a high pressure (HP) turbine where, after suffering an expansion process is extracted at B in order to reheat it. The reheated steam is left to its expansion through a low pressure (LP) turbine up to E in the second case and up to D in the rest, obtaining the required power. In Configuration 1 (PT-CSP + RO, Fig. 1), the desalination process is driven by the power output from the CSP plant. The desalination plant considered in Configuration 2 (PT-CSP + LT-MED, Fig. 2) is fed at F by the low temperature steam from the turbine outlet after being reheated to obtain saturated steam without increasing the temperature. Finally, in Configuration 3 (PT-CSP + LT-MED-TVC, Fig. 3), part of the steam at B is used as motive steam in a steam ejector after passing through a reheater to achieve saturation conditions, using the exhaust steam from the turbine at D as entrained vapour in the ejector. The resulting compressed vapour from the ejector is injected into the first effect of the distillation unit at F, driving the thermal desalination process. Table 1 presents the operating conditions that have been considered in the schemes proposed, which will be used as inputs for the following simulations.

The net power of the CSP plant has been considered in all configurations to be 50 MW_e, which is the standard current design of many commercial parabolic trough CSP plants [12]. In the turbine, with the exception of Configuration 2 explained above, the steam is allowed to expand up to 37°C (0.063 bar), which is the design turbine exit pressure for Andasol-1 CSP plant in Spain ([8]).

2.2 Simulations

The integrated power and desalination cycle has been simulated using the Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software [13], assuming a steady state operation. Table 2 gives an overview on the main parameters and assumptions used in the thermodynamic simulation. The specific electric consumption of the RO plant has been considered to be the same as the desalination plant located in Barcelona and in the case of MED plant, the value of 2.2 kWh/m³ includes the pumping of seawater at 3 km distance for the condenser. Main plant operating conditions detailed above are fed to the software as input variables. The solution provides for each configuration the mass flow rates flowing through the HP and LP turbine, the motive steam and the entrained vapour mass flow rates in the steam ejector, and the mass flow rate feeding the MED plant. Moreover, the net output thermal capacity (thermal power to be provided by the solar field) and the overall efficiency are obtained from the integrated power and desalination cycle simulation. Subsequently, the gross turbine output, the water mass flow rate required in the condenser (in the case that wet cooling is used to condense the exhaust steam) and the total water production are calculated.

The simulation has been done first for Configurations 2 and 3, with the condition that the desalination plant replaces the condenser. This results in different values for the gross water production in the desalination system, which is determined by the mass flow of the exhaust steam in each case. The gross fresh water production in Configurations 2 and 3 is calculated by:

$$FWF_{gross} = q_{exhaust} \cdot GOR \quad (1)$$

where FWF_{gross} is the gross fresh water production in m^3/day , and GOR is Gained Output Ratio, which is defined as kilograms of distillate produced for every kilogram of steam supplied to the distillation unit. In the case of Configuration 3, to calculate the steam ejector flow rates (both live and entrained vapour flow rates), the semi-empirical model developed by El-Dessouky [14] has been considered. The model makes use of the field data collected over 35 years by Power [15] for vapour entrainment ratios of steam jet ejectors. The entrainment ratio is the mass flow rate ratio of the motive steam and the entrained vapor and it can be calculated using the following correlation [14]:

$$Ra = 0.296 \frac{(P_s)^{1.19}}{(P_{ev})^{1.04}} \left(\frac{P_m}{P_{ev}} \right)^{0.015} \left(\frac{PCF}{TCF} \right) \quad (2)$$

where P_m , P_s and P_{ev} are the pressures of the motive steam, compressed vapor and entrained vapor respectively, PCF is the motive steam pressure correction factor and TCF is the entrained vapor temperature correction factor. Following equations were used to calculate both, PCF and TCF ([14]):

$$PCF = 3 \times 10^{-7} (P_m)^2 - 0.0009 (P_m) + 1.6101 \quad (3)$$

$$TCF = 2 \times 10^{-8} (T_{ev})^2 - 0.0006 (T_{ev}) + 1.0047 \quad (4)$$

where P_m is in kPa and T_{ev} is in $^{\circ}C$.

The net fresh water production is slightly less than the gross fresh water production, since a small part of the distilled water produced is consumed internally in the plant for cleaning the mirrors ([16]). The best result from Configurations 2 and 3 is the value which has been taken as the net water production in the simulations for Configuration 1. In this case, when evaporative water cooling is considered an additional amount of water must be produced to be used in the cooling system.

Finally, the overall efficiency of the integrated power and desalination cycle has been calculated by:

$$\eta_{global} = P_{net} / NOTC \quad (5)$$

where $NOTC$ is the net output thermal capacity, which is the sum of the power required by the power conversion system (consisting of a pre-heater, an evaporator and a superheater) and the reheaters of the cycle, and P_{net} is the net power production of the system.

In the assessment of Configuration 1 with a dry air cooling system, the power required by the cooling unit has been taken from a study of a dry-cooled parabolic trough plant located in the Mojave Desert, which showed 5% less electric energy produced annually ([11])

The solar field has been simulated in order to determine its required size to provide the $NOTC$ of the integrated power and desalination cycle. It has been carried out by implementing a model in MATLAB. For this purpose, a model is used for the collector based on its thermal losses, its efficiency curve and energy balances ([20], [21], [22]). The model input parameters are:

- North-South orientation.
- Design point: 12th September (radiation at solar noon = 915.9 W/m^2 , ambient temperature = $26.21^{\circ}C$).
- Thermal storage capacity for 24-h operation at design day.
- The net output thermal capacity of the power block.
- Inlet temperature to the solar field ($295^{\circ}C$).
- Outlet temperature from the solar field ($390^{\circ}C$).

The simulation was carried out considering a coastal location with $1990 \text{ kWh/m}^2 \cdot \text{yr}$ of DNI radiation, which can also be considered as a good representative for CSP in Mediterranean areas. Radiation and ambient temperature data have been taken from a meteorological year type data generated with the software PVSYST V 4.36 (monthly horizontal global irradiance data, ambient temperature and wind velocity obtained with the Meteororm software [17]). The PT solar field is based on commercial LS-3 type collector (aperture area of 545 m^2 and a longitude of 99 m). The peak optical efficiency for this type of collectors is 76% and the thermal oil that circulates through the absorber tubes is Monsanto VP-1 (properties determined using Monsanto software).

2.3 Economic analysis

To carry out an estimation of the power and water costs of the configurations proposed, we will use the following definition of Levelized Electricity Cost (LEC) ([18]):

$$LEC = \frac{crf \times K_{invest} + K_{O\&M} + K_{fuel}}{E_{net}} \quad (6)$$

crf is the capital recovery factor, which is calculated by:

$$crf = \frac{k_d (1 + k_d)^n}{(1 + k_d)^n - 1} + k_{insurance} \quad (7)$$

where $K_{insurance}$ is the annual insurance rate, K_{invest} is the total investment of the plant, K_{fuel} is the annual fuel cost (which is only applicable in the case of solar energy with backup), k_d is the real debt interest rate, n is the depreciation period in years, $K_{O\&M}$ are the annual operation and maintenance costs and E_{net} is the annual net electricity delivered to the grid. In the cases studied, an annual insurance rate of 1% has been used, a real debt interest rate of 8% has been considered and the value used for the depreciation period is of 25 years. Moreover, around 10 hours of thermal storage in the CSP plant (working 24 hours from mid spring to mid autumn and also at nominal turbine capacity the rest of the year) and investments costs of 3300 €/kW_{nominal} and 40 €/kWh for the PT-CSP plant without thermal storage and for the thermal storage, respectively, have been considered. A plant availability of 96% has been taken into account and a consumption to be provided by the desalination plant of 0.07 m³/MWh_e for the cleaning of the mirrors has been taken ([16]). In the case of evaporative water cooling, the water needed by the power plant to be obtained from the desalination plant, has been considered to be 3 m³/MWh_e ([16]). The same procedure has been used for the Levelized Water Cost (LWC) estimation. For this assessment, investment costs of 850 €/m³ day installed (with an availability of 92%) and 1050 €/m³ day installed (with an availability of 98%) for the RO and MED facility, respectively, have been considered.

3. Results and discussion

Table 3 shows the results obtained from the simulation of Configurations 2 and 3 and their comparison. In Configuration 2 (CSP+LT-MED), a total water production of 47918 m³/day is obtained when all the steam from the turbine outlet at 70°C feeds the MED unit. In Configuration 3 (CSP+LT-MED-TVC), the HP turbine requires more steam (111.6 kg/s) to be produced, since part of it (81.88 kg/s) is later used as motive steam in the ejector. Subsequently, the rest of steam (29.75 kg/s) enters the LP turbine and then it is used as entrained vapour in the ejector. It can be observed that the configuration with LT-MED is more efficient than configuration with LT-MED-TVC from a thermodynamic point of view. In order to produce the same amount of net electricity (50W_e), a much smaller solar field is needed (about 44% smaller), and subsequently less steam is used in the turbine, less must be condensed and therefore the desalination unit is smaller. This means that the power penalty for reducing the expansion of the steam in the LP turbine to extract it from the outlet at higher pressure is lower than the power penalty when part of the high pressure steam that leaves the HP turbine is used for the ejector with the full exhaust steam from the LP turbine. Therefore, the coupling with a LT-MED has been chosen as the most feasible option for replacing the condenser in the CSP plant

The net fresh water production obtained by Configuration 2, 47802 m³/day, has been taken as an input parameter in the simulations of Configuration 1. The objective is to compare the CSP+D concept without the condenser with the standard power cycle with no power production penalty, although with an increased gross power demand to feed a RO desalination unit, which has a larger specific electrical consumption than the LT-MED. Different types of cooling have been considered and compared in this Configuration 1. Table 3 show the results obtained from the simulations using both types of wet cooling, once-through and evaporative water cooling, as well as dry air cooling. It also depicts a comparison with respect to the configuration with LT-MED. Unlike in Configuration 2, in Configuration 1 all the steam produced through the power conversion system of the power cycle (54.25 kg/s in the case of once-through

cooling, 51.55 kg/s in the case of evaporative water cooling and 53.97 kg/s in the case of dry cooling) must be condensed, since no extraction is done at the outlet of the turbine. From the comparison, it can be observed that Configuration 1 is the most efficient from a thermodynamic point of view (the lowest NOTC, the largest overall efficiency and the smallest solar field). This means that the higher steam pressure at the outlet of the turbine in Configuration 2 penalizes the power production with respect to Configuration 1, as expected, and this penalty is large enough to overcome the saving in gross power production due to the LT-MED having less electrical consumption than the RO. This latter fact, which is true for Mediterranean conditions, could change if the seawater conditions (salinity and temperature) require a larger specific electrical consumption of the RO process, as is the case of the Arabian Gulf ([19]). The cost of water is higher for Configuration 2 due to the higher investment costs of the MED plant compared to the RO.

Regarding the cooling systems, as mentioned above, no cooling is required for the power cycle in the case which integrates a MED system. Comparing the different systems in Configuration 1, it can be observed that evaporative water cooling is the most efficient thermodynamically. Economically, the levelized cost of electricity and water are 0.8% and 1.5% lower than in the CSP+MED case. However, 4231 m³/day of fresh water are consumed in the condenser in this case and therefore the RO unit must be about 10% larger, which affects the investment costs. Subsequently, the LWC is higher for the evaporative cooling than in the case of the once-through wet cooling and the dry cooling. In these cases, however, although less water needs to be desalinated, the gross power production needs to be larger due to the high electrical consumption associated to the seawater circulation in the former and the fans in the latter. This has an effect on the LEC, which is higher for both cases (2.1% and 3.3% respectively), even surpassing that of Configuration 2. In addition, for the once-through cooling 131291 m³/day of seawater are required and environmental issues could have a limitation on the management of such quantities of seawater. Also, the cooling towers and water transport systems require special alloy and more intensive cleaning. Therefore, if the fresh water demands in the Mediterranean area require a CSP+D concept which maximizes the water production, the use of dry cooling could be considered a feasible option. Comparing this case with the simulation of Configuration 2, it can be observed that the LEC is lower in the latter, so it could be a viable alternative.

4. Conclusions

The paper presents a techno-economic analysis of different concepts for associating MED and RO desalination units with parabolic trough concentrating solar power (CSP) plants in the Mediterranean region. In the coupling of a CSP plant with a MED system which replaces the conventional cooling unit of the power cycle two alternatives have been compared. The configuration where the steam of the turbine is not left to expand completely but used as the input for the low-temperature MED plant, is more efficient than when thermal compression is considered to use the fully exhaust steam from the LP turbine fed into a steam ejector with higher pressure steam from the HP turbine.

The most optimum CSP+MED coupling has been compared with a CSP connected with a RO unit, where no modifications are made to the power cycle and a cooling system is required. It has been shown that this system is more thermodynamically efficient, since the additional electrical consumption of the RO does not surpass the penalization in the power production due to replacing the condenser with a MED plant. Economically the differences are not too large, though, and in some cases even favourable to the CSP+MED. Of the different cooling systems compared for the CSP+RO combination, the use of evaporative water cooling is the most efficient and economical in terms of the electricity production. However, additional production of fresh water is required in this case and the cost of water is higher than for the once-through wet cooling and the dry cooling systems. In these cases, however, there is a higher electrical demand by the seawater pumping and the fans, respectively, and the levelized electricity costs surpass those of the CSP+MED coupling.

The results provided will help design the most appropriate configuration according to the specific demands. However, they are dependent on the seawater properties, which affect the RO process strongly, and cannot be extrapolated to other regions where the seawater conditions (salinity and temperature) are not as optimal for the use of RO desalination as in the Mediterranean Sea.

Table captions

Table 1. Operating conditions of the schemes showed in Figs. 1, 2, 3.

Table 2. Main parameters and assumptions used in the thermodynamic simulation.

Table 3. Results obtained from the simulation of Configurations 2 and 3.

Table 4. Results obtained from the simulation of Configuration 2 and Configuration 1 using wet cooling (once-through and evaporative) and dry cooling.

Figure captions

Fig 1. Diagram of Configuration 1 (RO unit combined with a PT-CSP plant).

Fig 2. Diagram of Configuration 2 (LT-MED unit integration into a PT-CSP plant).

Fig 3. Diagram of Configuration 3 (LT-MED-TVC unit integration into a PT-CSP plant).

Nomenclature

crf	capital recovery factor
$CSP+D$	concentrating solar power and desalination
DNI	direct normal irradiance ($\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{yr}$)
EES	engineering Equation Solver
E_{net}	annual net electricity delivered to the grid
FWF_{gross}	gross fresh water production (m^3/day)
FWF_{net}	net fresh water production (m^3/day)
GOR	Gain Output Ratio
HP	high pressure
k_d	real debt interest rate
K_{fuel}	annual fuel cost
$k_{insurance}$	annual insurance rate
K_{invest}	total investment of the plant
$K_{O\&M}$	annual operation and maintenance costs
LEC	levelized electricity cost ($\text{€}/\text{kWh}$)
LWC	levelized water cost ($\text{€}/\text{m}^3$)
$LT-MED$	low temperature multi-effect distillation
$LT-MED-TVC$	low temperature multi-effect distillation powered by a thermal vapour compressor
LP	low pressure
$MENA$	Middle East and North Africa
$NOTC$	net output thermal capacity (MW)
PCF	motive steam pressure correction factor
P_{net}	net power production of the CSP+D system (MW)
P_{ev}	pressure of the entrained vapour (kPa)
P_m	pressure of the motive steam (kPa)
P_s	pressure of the compressed vapour (kPa)
PT	parabolic trough
$q_{exhaust}$	mass flow rate of the exhaust steam (kg/s)
Ra	entrained vapour
RO	reverse osmosis
TCF	entrained vapour temperature correction factor
$TVC-MED$	thermal vapour compression multi-effect distillation

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Table 1

Point A	371°C, 104 bar
Point B	17 bar
Point C	371 °C, 17 bar
Point D	37°C
Point E	70°C
Point F	70°C

Table 2

Isoentropic efficiency of the high pressure steam turbine (%)	85
Isoentropic efficiency of the low pressure turbine (%)	85
Isoentropic efficiency of the pumps (%)	85
Specific electric consumption of the LT-MED plant (kWh/m ³)	2.2
Specific electric consumption of the RO unit (kWh/m ³)	4.17
GOR of the LT-MED plant	9.8
Fresh water temperature (°C)	35
Fresh water pressure (bar)	1
Net power production of the system (MW _e)	50
Seawater needed in the once-through cooling (m ³ /MWh _e)	87 ^a
Water required in the evaporative water cooling (m ³ /MWh _e)	3 ^a

^a[16]

Table 3

	Steam in HP turbine (kg/s)	Motive steam in ejector (kg/s)	Entrained vapour in ejector (kg/s)	FWF _{gross} (m ³ /day)	FWF _{net^a} (m ³ /day)	Overall efficiency (%)	NOTC (MW)	Area of the solar field (m ²)
LT-MED	56.25	NA	NA	47918	47802	26.9	186	808780
LT-MED- TVC	111.6	81.88	29.75	95087	94881	15.1	331	1443160

^aThis amount is determined discounting internal consumption for mirror washing

Table 4

	LT-MED	RO (once-through cooling)	RO (evaporative water cooling)	RO (dry cooling)
Steam in the HP turbine (kg/s)	56.25	54.25	51.55	53.97
Water mirror washing (m ³ /day)	115.4	112.5	106.9	111.9
Seawater needed in the condenser (m ³ /day)	0	131291	NA	NA
Fresh water consumed in the condenser (m ³ /day)	0	NA	4231	NA
FWF _{gross} (m ³ /day)	47918	47914	52140	47914
FWF _{net} (m ³ /day)	47802	47802	47802	47802
NOTC (MW)	186	181	172	180
Gross power production (MW _e)	55	62.8	59.7	62.5
Overall efficiency (%)	26.9	27.6	29.1	27.8
Aperture area of the solar field (m ²)	808780	788070	748830	783710
LEC (€/kWh)	0.243	0.246	0.241	0.249
LWC (€/m ³)	0.919	0.844	0.905	0.844

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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Figure 3
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